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ReCreate

Reusing precast concrete for a circular economy

Vullings et al.

Real-life deconstruction pilots of the ReCreate project

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Abstract

The ReCreate project researches deconstruction and reuse of precast concrete elements, not originally designed for disassembly. ReCreate's real-life pilots are a significant tool for achieving this goal. This report describes and illustrates ReCreate's deconstruction pilots.

Six real-life deconstructions of precast concrete buildings – one in Finland, two in Sweden, one in the Netherlands, and two in Germany – are used in the ReCreate project to generate theoretical and practical knowledge about a wide range of topics directly related to the process of salvaging and reusing precast concrete elements. While the learnings regarding the planning and implementation of deconstruction are described in a centralised manner in another report (Vullings et al. 2024), the current report documents the donor buildings of the secondary elements as well as their practical deconstruction processes through textual descriptions and generous photographic illustrations and drawings. The donor buildings were blocks of flats (three buildings), public and private office buildings (two buildings) and industrial/warehouse buildings (one building). They had been deemed obsolete and were therefore slated for demolition. When engaged in ReCreate, they instead became vessels of knowledge generation for reuse-minded deconstruction. The various elements reclaimed from the donor buildings, such as sandwich panels, massive concrete slabs, massive interior wall elements, hollow core slabs, beams, and columns, will be reused in future in ReCreate's reuse pilots. In addition to ReCreate's six donor buildings, insights from following and observing two additional deconstructions, external to ReCreate, are also reported on herein.

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1. Introduction

One of the key tasks in the ReCreate project is the deconstruction of precast concrete elements from real-life donor buildings, six in total, to be reused in the project's reuse pilots. In this report, a short presentation of the deconstruction process of each of the donor buildings (Figure 1) is given to showcase the successful implementation of the deconstructions. Another deconstruction-related ReCreate report (Vullings et al. 2024) synthesises and summarises the combined key learnings from the pilots.

Finland (photo: Heikki Vuorinen, TAU)

Netherlands (photo: T. Lambrechts, TU/e)

Sweden, donor 1 (photo: Helsingborgshem)

Sweden, donor 2 (photo: Helsingborg city)

Germany, donor 1 (photo: C. Henschel, BTU)

Germany, donor 2 (photo: A. Mettke, BTU)

Figure 1. Six donor buildings of the ReCreate project.

Next, each donor building and deconstruction project is described in a dedicated chapter, country by country.

However, some of the ReCreate partners were not only involved in the deconstruction of the ReCreate pilots but also in other projects (Figure 2). Some of the processes used in these additional projects were monitored by the partners and the research data and experiences will be used in the ReCreate project. The additional data will be incorporated in several work packages and in order to provide a complete scope of all the deconstructed projects, the additional projects are also described in Chapter 6 of this report.

Figure 2. Two additional deconstruction projects monitored. Office building Ter Haak in the Netherlands (left) and a block of flats in Grimma, Germany (right) (photos: Ter Haak [left] and Jacob Fischer [right], BTU).

2. Finland

2.1. Description of the project

The Finnish deconstruction pilot was an office building in Tampere city centre. It was originally built in 1982 for the insurance company 'Kansa', and one of its latest users was the insurance company 'Pohjantähti'. Thus, the building was lately colloquially known as the 'House of Pohjantähti', though its official registered name was 'Kiinteistö Oy Kyttälänkontu' (Property Ltd Kyttälänkontu). The building was slated for demolition to change the land use of the plot from offices to housing. The City of Tampere renewed the urban plan to enable the construction of a new block of flats. The plot, including the building, was acquired by the construction company Skanska, a ReCreate industrial partner, to implement the new housing. Skanska engaged the slated building in the ReCreate project to act as the Finnish deconstruction pilot. The deconstruction works were implemented in collaboration by Skanska and the demolition company Umacon, another ReCreate industrial partner.

The building was appraised as a favourable case for deconstruction for two reasons. Firstly, the reasons for decommissioning were not connected with the technical condition of the building's structure, which was estimated to be good. Second, the structure was made of load-bearing columns, beams, and hollow core slabs, which were deemed as favourable element types for deconstruction due to the connections used between them. It was estimated that the connections used could be successfully undone.

The facades of the building were also made of precast elements. They were blind (i.e. windowless) sandwich elements, where a layer of mineral wool insulation was located between two concrete planes tied together with steel trusses. The sandwich facade elements came as so-called strip elements (between the windows) and as storey height elements. These facade elements were not deemed as favourable for reuse for two reasons. Firstly, precast concrete facades of this era were usually not made with frost-resistant concrete, which enables freeze-thaw deterioration to occur in the external panel and so limits the service life in reuse in the Nordic climate of Finland. Indeed, a condition investigation performed on the facades some years earlier confirmed that some deterioration had already taken place. Second, the mineral wool insulation that these elements contain is a possible source of indoor air quality problems. This is a particular concern if the mineral wool gets wet during the deconstruction, transportation, or storage, either due to rainwater or the water used to cool down the deconstruction equipment, such as diamond saws. Because health concerns connected to indoor air quality problems are a topical and highly sensitive issue in Finland, it was estimated that clients would be reluctant towards the reuse of elements that contain mineral wool. Therefore, the facade elements were deselected from reuse in large quantities. Nevertheless, they had to be deconstructed to enable the columns, beams, and hollow core slabs to be harvested from the building. Therefore, a handful of them was preserved to document their condition and to study the potential for reuse.

2. 2. Location of the donor building

The donor building’s location is given in Figure 3 and Figure 4. The plot is a corner plot, the address of which are Aleksanterinkatu 21 and Kyttälänkatu 5, Tampere.

Figure 3. Map of Finland (left), base map source: National Land Survey of Finland, map service ‘Karttapaiikka’. The donor building was located in Tampere (red dot). For reference, the capital Helsinki is marked with a blue dot. Map of Tampere (right), base map source: City of Tampere, map service ‘Oskari’. The rough location of the donor building in the city centre (purple dot).

Figure 4. Map of Tampere city centre, base map source: City of Tampere, map service ‘Oskari’. Location of the donor building marked with a red dot (addresses Aleksanterinkatu 21/Kyttälänkatu 5).

2. 3. Donor building

2.3.1. Building geometry

The building had two wings, the main wing with seven floors and the other with only one floor (Figure 5). The footprint of the main wing was 29,6 m by 14,7 m and its height was 25,5 m. The footprint of the one-floor wing was 21,2 m by 22,0 m and its height was 4,9 m.

On the plot, there was also a cold canopy, covering the driveway to the courtyard, where overground parking was located, as well as to the subterranean parking garage. On the basement floor of the building, in addition to the aforementioned parking garage, also storage spaces, and engineering and utility services room were located. On the ground floor, there was also a swimming pool. Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the exterior of the building prior to deconstruction. Figure 7 and Figure 8 depict the interiors, both before and during the deconstruction.

Figure 5. Finnish donor building and plot (circled with red) in August 2022 (photo: Heikki Vuorinen, TAU).

Figure 6. The building in August 2022, Kyttälänkatu side (left) and the short side of the building as seen from the neighbouring plot (right), photos: Heikki Vuorinen, TAU.

Figure 7. Interiors of the building before deconstruction. The open plan achieved with the columns (left) was mostly divided into office rooms with drywalls (right), photos: Jaakko Kinnunen.

Figure 8. The interior during deconstruction. After the internal stripping, the open plan is fully visible (photo: Heikki Vuorinen, TAU).

2.3.2. Structure of the building

A set of drawings and documents pertaining to the building were found in the archives of the building inspection authority of the City of Tampere. These are digitized (scanned) versions of the original paper documents, which have been replaced with the digitized copies. The uncovered documentation contained architectural drawings (Figure 9 and Figure 10), structural drawings (Figure 11 and Figure 12), and shop drawings (Figure 13). However, some drawings belonging to these sets had also either gone missing or had not originally been archived. These include, for instance, the architect’s first-floor plan drawing and precast element drawings for hollow core slabs.

Figure 9. Original facade drawing of the west facade (Aleksanterinkatu side) by the architect Ilkka Pyykkö. Example of the architectural drawings (source: City of Tampere archives).

Figure 10. Original plan drawing of the 5th storey by the architect Ilkka Pyykkö, in the same position with the facade in figure 8. The layout of the office spaces differed slightly storey by storey. The layouts were achieved with non-load-bearing drywalls, and the underlying precast concrete structure was the same in each floor (source: City of Tampere archives).

Figure 11. Original structural ceiling drawing of the 4th storey (i.e. floor of the 5th storey), showing the division into slab elements. Compare with the architectural plan in figure 9. Example of structural drawings by the engineering office Suunnittelutieto Oy (source: City of Tampere archives).

Figure 12. Original structural drawing of beams. Example of structural drawings by the engineering office Suunnittelutiето Oy (source: City of Tampere archives).

Figure 13. Original precast drawing of beams. Example of structural drawings by the engineering office Suunnittelutiето Oy (source: City of Tampere archives).

The foundation of the building consisted of in situ-cast wall and column footings, which were connected to piles. The foundation plan of the plot can be seen in Figure 14, where the grid lines E3 – H9 are the foundations of the main wing of the building.

The basement floor of the main wing consisted of load bearing walls, which were connected to the footings with vertical ties (Figure 15). On the ground floor, the vertical load-bearing structures were columns, which were connected to the slab and wall structures of the basement floor, except in the grid line H3-H9 where the columns were connected directly

to the column footings with vertical ties. The columns were connected to the slab and walls with welded connection or vertical ties (Figure 16). The same welded connection was used in the other floors as well to connect the columns to the beams (Figure 17). The beams were connected to the columns with single centric dowel connections. In the deconstruction, the welded connections were exposed from concrete by chiselling and steel connections were cut off.

The hollow core slabs were positioned on the beams, and on the load-bearing facade elements and wall elements. Non-load-bearing facade elements were connected to the sides of the hollow core slabs. In addition, the hollow core slabs were connected to each other with horizontal ties between each slab. Each floor was also tied with horizontal hooped reinforcement to brace the whole floor structure. The connections of the hollow core slabs are presented in the Figure 18. During the deconstruction, the ties were cut off with a diamond saw.

Each facade element was connected to the floor structure. The hollow core slabs were placed on the facade elements and connected to them with vertical ties. The non-load-bearing facade elements were connected to the sides of the hollow core slabs with 2-3 ties each. The facade elements were connected to similar elements above and below with vertical ties, and to the horizontally neighbouring elements with vertical and horizontal ties. The connections of the facade elements are presented in Figure 19. The ties were cut off before the elements were detached.

The building frame was braced with the help of two in-situ cast elevator and staircase shafts.

All reinforcement and ties cut off during deconstruction must be redesigned and/or renewed before the elements can be reused.

Figure 14. Original foundation and pile plan (source: City of Tampere archives).

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Figure 15. Original drawing of section 3-3. Connections between the footing and the load-bearing wall structure of basement floor as well as a column of the main wing (source: City of Tampere archives).

Figure 16. Original drawing of sections 6-6 and 7-7. Connection of basement wall structures to columns on the ground floor (source: City of Tampere archives).

Figure 17. Original detail drawing of a column-beam-column connection (source: City of Tampere archives).

Figure 18. Original drawings of connections between hollow core slabs and facade elements, and between two hollow core slabs (source: City of Tampere archives).

Figure 19. Original drawings of connections of facade elements, (source: City of Tampere archives).

2. 4. Deconstruction

The deconstruction was implemented in collaboration by the construction company Skanska and the deconstruction company Umacon. The donor building and its site are owned by Skanska, thus Skanska possessed the responsibility to manage and oversee the deconstruction works. In addition to the site managers, Skanska dedicated a tower crane driver and an experienced precast concrete assembler to the site. Together with them, Umacon was responsible for the implementation of the deconstruction works. The deconstruction encompassed the following main phases (in chronological order):

1. Asbestos and hazardous substance removal,
2. Internal stripping to reveal the structural frame,
3. Deconstruction of the precast elements (floors 3–7),
4. Demolition of the remaining structure (floors –1–2).

The deconstruction site was fenced off at the end of May 2023 (Figure 20). The main phases 1 and 2, i.e. asbestos and hazardous substance removal and internal stripping of the structure, are preparatory works that were conducted between June and August. Phase 1, i.e. the asbestos and hazardous substance removal, was conducted in a normal manner.

Figure 20. The site in mid-June (photo: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

By contrast, it was necessary to do Phase 2, the internal stripping, to a ‘cleaner’ level than normally would be done, either in a demolition project or a renovation project. Most importantly, a layer of screed was removed from the surface of the hollow core slabs (Figure 21). On top of the screed, a vinyl floor covering had been glued. In the glue, volatile organic compounds (VOCs) had been detected. The glue was removed as part of the asbestos and hazardous substance removal. However, it was deemed possible that the screed could have absorbed traces of VOCs. The screed was removed to ensure that no traces of VOCs could be passed on as a part of the deconstructed elements. This was ensured by field measurements of VOCs by the engineers of Ramboll before and after the removal of the screed.

Additionally, the Finnish cluster reflected whether paints could most effectively be stripped from the elements if conducted in the donor building prior to deconstruction, or after deconstruction as a part of the factory refurbishment. Therefore, it was decided that for a part of the elements, the paint would be sanded down as a part of the internal stripping (Figure 22), while in case of other elements, it would be left for the factory refurbishment phase. The tower crane to lift the elements down was installed in mid-August 2023 (Figure 23).

Figure 21. The screed is removed using a demolition robot (photos: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

Figure 22. The paint from the bottom of the hollow core slabs is grinded off. The screed has been removed revealing the seams between hollow core slabs (photo: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

Figure 23. Crane assembly ongoing (photo: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

Before deconstruction, each element was marked to be able to trace them after they leave the building (Figure 24). Lifting holes were pre-drilled to all floor and wall elements and columns. The elements were shored, as if constructing a building from elements, to provide safety for the workers (Figure 25). The shoring was removed as the elements were dismantled.

Figure 24. The elements were marked with individual codes before deconstruction (photo: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

Figure 25. Bracing and lifting holes (photo: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

Diamond saws were used to detach the elements from each other (Figure 26). Seams between hollow core slabs and massive slabs were sawed with a remote-controlled wall saw and seams between hollow core slabs with a floor saw. The connections between beams and columns were drilled (Figure 27). A hand-held saw was used for wall elements and column-to-slab connections.

Figure 26. Sawing hollow core slabs with floor saw (left) and detaching a column with a hand saw (right), photos: Emmi Salmio, TAU.

Figure 27. The connection of a beam and a column was drilled in a way that the original steel connections were not cut, and they can be further used in connecting the elements (photo: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

A demolition robot, the same used for removing the screed, was used to chisel seams between wall elements and their connections to hollow core slabs (Figure 28). The robot was also used to give a push to hollow core slabs and beams, and to push down columns while they were attached to the crane to detach them from surrounding elements.

Figure 28. Demolition robot is used for chiselling the connection between hollow core slabs and facade elements (on the left) and between two facade elements (on the right), photos: Emmi Salmio, TAU.

The elements were attached to the crane before fully detaching them. Each element was connected to the crane and lifted only after making sure that the element was fully detached (Figure 29). Any connecting bits were either sawed with diamond saw or chiseled using the demolition robot.

Figure 29. Lifting of a massive slab (on the left) and a hollow core slab (on the right), photos: Emmi Salmio, TAU.

A special lifting accessory was designed and manufactured to lift the hollow core slabs (Figure 29). The columns were lifted using lifting pins, slid through a hole in the column. Beams were lifted with two slings around the ends of the beam. Wall elements and massive slabs were lifted using web and chain slings pulled through the drill holes. Even though not all elements, especially wall elements, were to be reused, almost all of them were detached and lifted down with the crane.

After the elements were lifted down, they were cleaned at the site removing all excess concrete etc. to provide homogenous quality and to ensure that nothing would fall off in transportation (Figure 30). The cleaning was done using hand tools and a power drill. (Figure 31). Each element was tagged with an individual QR code (Figure 32). Elements were briefly stored at the site before the transportation to the element factory (Figure 33).

Figure 30. Columns before cleaning (left) and cleaned and tagged columns (right). Due to the disassembly method, the connection steel bars are left on the columns. (photos: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

Figure 31. Cleaning of hollow core slabs (photo: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

Figure 32. After the elements were lifted down and cleaned, they were tagged with QR tags containing their individual codes (photo: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

Figure 33. Elements are stored at the site for a short period before transportation (photo: Emmi Salmio, TAU).

The deconstruction ended in the end of November 2023. The tower crane was dismantled in December 2023. The decommissioning of the remaining floors continued using conventional destructive demolition methods. Figure 34 to Figure 40 show the progression of the deconstruction.

Figure 34. The building at the start of deconstruction (photo: TAU).

Figure 35. 7th floor (photo: TAU).

Figure 36. 6th floor (photo: TAU).

Figure 37. 5th floor (photo: TAU).

Figure 38. 4th floor (photo: TAU).

Figure 39. 3rd floor (photo: TAU).

Figure 40. 2nd floor, the end of deconstruction. The remaining structure was demolished (photo: TAU).

2. 5. Storage of the harvested elements

The reclaimed elements were transported (Figure 41) to Consolis Parma precast concrete factory in Kangasala (Figure 42), where they are stored (Figure 43) until they are factory-refurbished in the same facility before reuse. The elements were transported following the practices and guidelines of transporting new elements, by a transport operator accustomed to transporting precast concrete elements. The transportation distance was 13 kilometers. Table 1 lists the number of reclaimed elements.

Figure 41. Transportation of harvested hollow core slabs; lorry leaving from the deconstruction site towards the Consolis Parma factory in Kangasala (photo: Satu Huuhka, TAU).

Figure 42. Location of the factory refurbishment facility, where the elements are stored (black dot; address Mäkirinteentie 19, Kangasala). Tampere city centre (circled) for reference. Base map source: City of Tampere, map service 'Oskari'.

Figure 43. Elements weather protected with tarps on outdoor storage field at Consolis Parma precast concrete factory in Kangasala (source: Satu Huuhka, TAU).

Table 1. Inventory of the precast concrete elements harvested from the Finnish deconstruction project. Notes: the Finnish donor project focus is in reusing the load-bearing frame, i.e. columns, beams and hollow core slabs. Therefore, other elements were saved only for test purposes, a small number of each type. Of the harvested elements, 9 hollow core slabs, 6 columns and 6–8 beams are dedicated to full-scale testing in a laboratory and thus will not be available for reuse. Photos: TAU/Emmi Salmio (Pi, L, V), Eetu Lehmusvaara (Pa, S) & Satu Huuhka (OL, N).

Code	Type	Description	Thumbnail	Number of elements
Pi	column	columns, two types (depending on the location – near the facade or in the middle of the building)		95
Pa	beam	beams, two lengths		45
OL	hollow core slab	hollow core slabs located near the facades		134
L	massive slab with integrated beams	massive concrete slabs, located in the middle of the building, integrated beams on two sides		3
S	exterior wall (room-sized panel)	blind load-bearing sandwich wall panels		3

N	exterior wall (strip panel)	blind non-load-bearing sandwich wall panels located between windows in the vertical direction		3
V	interior wall	blind massive concrete wall panels surrounding a staircase (on the left in the photo)		3

2. 6. Available project documents

One of the preparations for deconstruction is the collection of project data, such as architectural designs, drawings and calculations from the structural engineer, and drawings and calculations from the precast suppliers. This data forms the basis for the rest of the demolition process, such as the development of the deconstruction plan, as well as the engineering process for the new building using the precast concrete elements that have been harvested.

During the preparation of the Finnish deconstruction pilot the following data was collected:

- Architectural drawings
 - Site plan (scale 1:200)
 - Floor plans, sections, and elevations (1:100)
- Structural drawings and calculations
 - Element layouts in facades (1:100)
 - Element layouts in floor plans (1:50)
 - Structural section drawings (1:20)
 - Foundation drawings (1:20 or 1:50)
 - Connection details (1:10 or 1:5)
 - Structural calculations
- Shop drawings
 - Precast element drawings (1:20) for all element types but hollow-core slabs
 - A list of hollow-core slabs by the precast factory

3. Sweden

3.1. Description of the projects

Two donor buildings and factory-rejected hollow core slabs make up the reclaimed elements for the Swedish reuse pilot, a temporary exhibition pavilion for the H22 city expo¹, which was implemented in 2022:

- Three precast concrete walls came from a block of flats in Drottninghög neighbourhood in Helsingborg, address *Grönkullagatan 1* (Figure 44 and Figure 45). These elements were salvaged prior to the ReCreate project, in preparation for it (the building's decommissioning could not wait for the ReCreate to commence).
- Columns with foundations and beams were harvested from an industrial building 'Huggjärnet' close to Drottninghög in Helsingborg (Figure 46).
- The hollow core slabs were factory rejects from the ReCreate project partner Strängbetong.

3.2. Location of the donor buildings

The donor buildings stood in Helsingborg, Sweden, about 60 km north of Malmö (Figure 44).

Figure 44. An overview of Helsingborg, including the location of the donor buildings is marked (Google maps).

¹ See <https://h22.se/en> for more information about the expo.

Figure 45. Donor building 1: Drottninghög - Grönkullagatan 1, 254 57 Helsingborg (source: Google maps).

Figure 46. Donor building 2: Huggjärnet - Kastellgatan 2, 254 66 Helsingborg (source: Google maps).

3. 3. Donor buildings

3.3.1. Building geometry

Drottninghög

The first donor building at Grönkullagatan 1 was a three-storey building that was a part of multiple rows of multi-family buildings constructed in the Drottninghög Västra 1 area in 1967

(Figure 47). Three of these buildings were demolished (Grönkullagatan 1,3 and 7) just before the beginning of the ReCreate project, so only a few of the elements from Grönkullagatan 1 could be harvested for reuse.

The building at Grönkullagatan 1 consisted of two equal building sections, Grönkullagatan 1A and 1B, each with a separate entrance and stairwell with two apartments on each landing. Each building section had a footprint of about 12 x 18 m and a height of 12,5 m.

Figure 47. A photograph showing the blocks of flats in Drottninghög (photo: Helsingborgshem).

Huggjärnet

The second donor building was a one-storey industrial building (Figure 48). It was constructed in 1966 and consisted of two parts: a warehouse and an adjacent office. The office was not a part of the deconstruction; only the precast concrete elements of the warehouse were harvested for reuse for the ReCreate project.

The floor plan of the warehouse was rectangular, about 29 m x 90 m. The building had a height of about 6,5 meters. One short facade was blind, and the other one was connected to the office. Both long facades of the building had large doors for easy access to the warehouse.

In the middle of the warehouse, a small area for offices and a reception was reserved. Left and right of this area were the open storage areas with a crane system providing lifting capacity to one side of the building. The crane system was integrated into the structure of the building.

FASAD MOT SÖDER

FASAD MOT NORR

FASAD MOT ÖSTER

Figure 48. Different views of the industrial building Huggjärnet (photos: Helsingborg municipality).

3.3.2. Structure of the buildings

Drottninghög

Figure 49 shows the original construction of the concrete structure of the block of flats. The structure consists of load-bearing precast concrete walls and solid concrete floor slabs. The facades at each end of the building were blind load-bearing walls. Within the building, the internal walls were also load-bearing and are indicated in the structural designs with the letter 'V' (Figure 50 and Figure 51). The precast concrete floor slabs are indicated with the letter 'P'. All the floor slabs were supported by two load-bearing walls. This indicates that all walls must have been load-bearing. The facade elements at the front and back of the

building were infill walls with insulation between timber studs and brick and concrete cladding. The stability of the structure was provided by the collaboration between all load-bearing walls and floor slabs.

Figure 49. Drottninghög blocks of flats under construction (photo: AB Helsingborgs-Bild).

Figure 50. Floor plan of the multi-family building at Drottninghög (source: Helsingborg Municipality).

Figure 51 shows the floor plans of the building. All the precast concrete walls and floor slabs have a unique identifier: a letter followed by a number. The unique identifiers connect all the design documents directly to the physical elements.

Figure 51. The floor plan of one building section (3 apartments), detail of Figure 50 (source: Helsingborg Municipality).

Huggjärnet

The industrial building had a precast column-beam structure with a few facade walls providing the structure with the necessary stability. There were three rows of columns along the long side of the warehouse. At each end, there were closed facade walls which provided the building stability in the transversal direction. Facade elements and internal walls in the middle of the building provide the stability of the building in the longitudinal direction. On top of the columns, concrete beams sat and supported the roof of the building.

Figure 52. A cross section of the warehouse – the original structural design of the building (source: Helsingborg Municipality).

An internal crane system was positioned on the concrete columns via concrete corbels. A cross section of the building shows the crane (Figure 52). The horizontal forces from the crane and the wind were transferred to the foundation of the building via bracing walls.

The columns were directly positioned on a concrete foundation base. Foundation beams were positioned on the foundation bases and provided support for the facade elements and bracing walls.

Figure 53 and Figure 54 provide longitudinal and transversal external elevations of the facades of the building. Most of the facades have no structural function in the building, only the walls at the short end of the warehouse provide some stability. Several cross sections of the building give a complete overview of the building and the structural design of the building (Figure 55).

Figure 53. Longitudinal elevations of the warehouse 'Huggjärnet' (source: Helsingborg Municipality).

Figure 54. Transversal elevations of the warehouse 'Huggjärnet' (source: Helsingborg Municipality).

Figure 55. Cross section of the warehouse 'Huggjärnet' (source: Helsingborg Municipality).

The floor plan of the warehouse is presented in Figure 56. The purple area is the warehouse itself, the green area is the adjacent office. There is a mezzanine in the warehouse (yellow area), which is located on the yellow dotted line (the left side of the warehouse, purple area). The office and the mezzanine are not part of the deconstruction.

Figure 56. Floor plan of the warehouse (right) and office-building (left), source: Helsingborg Municipality, ameded.

3. 4. Deconstruction

Drottninghög

Figure 57 shows the back view of the block of flats with parts of the facade panels stripped. The facade elements on the long side of the building were not precast concrete elements and therefore not a part of the ReCreate project.

Figure 57. The deconstruction site during deconstruction (source: Helsingborgshem).

The lifting of the solid concrete floor slabs is shown in Figure 58. Fasteners were installed into the slabs for lifting the slabs. Only two fasteners were used in order to limit possible damage to the elements themselves as well as the amount of drilling. This meant that the positioning of the fasteners needed to be rather accurate in order to keep the slabs level during the lifting process.

Figure 58. Lifting and transporting of the floor slabs (photo: Jonas Linné).

Figure 59. The building after the stripping of the facades (photo: Helsingborg Municipality).

First, all the façade elements were removed to reveal the precast concrete structure (Figure 59). Of all the precast concrete elements (walls and floor slabs) only a handful were deconstructed for reuse, mainly because the decommissioning was to move forward for timetabling reasons before the ReCreate project could officially start.

Huggjärnet

Figure 60 shows the structure of the warehouse when all but the structural elements have been stripped and the columns and beams can be seen. On the right, the columns with the corbels are visible; this is where the crane was located.

Figure 60. The columns and beams of the warehouse (photo: Helsingborgshem).

3. 5. Storage of the harvested elements

Figure 61. Transport of concrete floor slabs to a storage facility in Helsingborg (photo: Helsingborgshem).

All the precast concrete elements were transported to a temporary storage facility (NSR AB Recyclingcentrum, Hjortshögsvägen 1, 254 64 Helsingborg). Figure 61 shows how the floor slabs were transported. They are not stacked on top of each other during the transport, but rather next to each other in order to prevent damage to the slabs. Figure 62 and Figure 63 show the temporary storage and transport of the beams and columns. Table 2 gives an inventory of the salvaged elements.

Figure 62. Storing of the columns and beams on the deconstruction site (source: Helena Westerlind, KTH).

Figure 63. Lifting of the columns onto a transport vehicle. The foundation of the columns were also reused (source: Helena Westerlind, KTH).

Table 2. Inventory of the number of theoretically available precast concrete elements. Notes: *This is the number of precast elements per floor, per block of apartments (with one block per entrance and stairwell with two apartments per landing. Notes: * The number of hollow core slabs used in the H22 pilot. Photos: Helsingborgshem.

Code	Type	Description	Thumbnail	Number of elements*
V	walls	load-bearing walls all walls are internal walls		20
P	floor slabs	massive concrete slabs		24
C	columns	two types of columns, with or without one corbel		50
B	beams	beams with a rectangle cross section		19
F	hollow core slabs	slabs rejected by the factory		7*

After the H22 City Expo, the exhibition pavilion where the elements were reused was deconstructed, and the precast concrete elements were transported to a storage facility where they awaited their next destination. However, they were later discarded, because no further reuse could be identified for them within a reasonable timeframe.

3. 6. Available project documents

During and after the Swedish deconstruction pilot and for the pilot for the H22 Expo the following data was collected:

Drottninghög

- Site plan of Drottninghög (scale 1:1000)
- Structural drawings of floor plans at Drottninghög (scale 1:100).
- Prefab element drawings for Drottninghög (scale 1:20)
- Several details for Drottninghög (scale 1:5)
- External elevations of Drottninghög (scale 1:100)
- Applications for demolition permit Drottninghög
- Historical photographs from Helsingborgs museum

Huggjärnet

- Site plan of Huggjärnet (scale 1:400)
- Structural drawings of floor plans Huggjärnet (scale 1:100)
- Section drawings of Huggjärnet (scale 1:100)
- Several details for Huggjärnet (scale 1:10)
- External elevations of Huggjärnet (scale 1:100)
- Application for demolition for Huggjärnet with numerous drawings

4. The Netherlands

4.1. Description of the project

The donor building in the Netherlands was an office building in the city centre of Arnhem (address Prinsenhof 1). The building was called 'Prinsenhof' and it was owned and used by the Province of Gelderland. The province had several office buildings in Arnhem.

The province slated the building for demolition, but wanted to do it in an environmentally friendly fashion. The demolition company Lagemaat, a ReCreate industrial partner, engaged the building in the ReCreate project by offering to deconstruct it and to reuse the harvested elements as structural elements in a new building.

The Prinsenhof was well suited for deconstruction and reuse because of its rather simple structural design and high repetition of precast concrete elements. The structure of the building was the same for every floor of the building and the number of different types of precast elements was limited: only load-bearing facade elements, floor slabs and precast concrete inner walls (or so-called 'core elements'). The building had two identical wings with a concrete core in the corner of the L-shaped building. The wings had an open floor plan and the facilities, such as a staircase, a lift and amenities (restrooms, pantries and storage space), were all located in the 'core' of the building.

4. 2. Location of the donor building

The location of the donor building in the Netherlands was Arnhem (Figure 64). For reference, a few well-known cities are also shown.

Figure 64. Map of the Netherlands with the location of the donor building (Arnhem) and the storage location of the harvested elements, also the final location of the new building at Heerde.

The map also includes the city Heerde, which is the location of the storage of the harvested precast concrete elements. It will also be the location of the reuse pilot. Figure 65 and Figure 66 show the location of the donor building in more detail.

Figure 65. Top view of Arnhem. The location of the city centre and the donor building are marked (source: Google Maps).

Figure 66. Location of the donor project (source: Google Maps).

4. 3. Donor building

4.3.1. Building geometry

The building had a L-shaped floor plan. The right wing of the building (part A, Figure 67) had nine floors, the left wing of the building (part B) had only five floors, and the core of the building located at their intersection (part C) had ten floors.

Figure 67. Left a top view of Prinsenhof and on the right the building is coloured purple (photos: Lagemaat, amended).

Figure 68. Three photographs of the exterior of the building (photos: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e).

Figure 69. Some photographs of the interior of the building (photos: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e).

Figure 68 provides an overview of the exterior of the building and Figure 69 gives an impression of the interior. The letters 'A' to 'C' refer to specific parts of the building indicated in Figure 67.

4.3.2. Structure of the building

In the archives of the building owner, province of Gelderland, the original project drawings and calculations were found. Figure 70 and Figure 71 show a few of the obtained drawings, including different parts of the building, the dimensions of the building and some structural aspects of the building.

Figure 70: Left floor plan 1 to 5 and right floor plan 6 to 9 (source: Province of Gelderland, amended)

These three main parts (A to C) of the building are also visible in the front views in Figure 71.

Figure 71. Front views of the outer facades of the building (source: Province of Gelderland, amended).

The building had a pile foundation. In situ cast concrete beams were placed on the piles. The ground floor consisted of insulated hollow core slabs (a typical Dutch product) that were placed on the foundation beams. Load-bearing sandwich facade elements were positioned on the foundations beams. The core walls were also positioned directly on the foundation beams. All elements were connected to the foundation beams with vertical ties. Prestressed hollow core slabs were placed on the facade elements and core walls. The floor slabs of the wings have a span of 12,7 m. At different locations horizontal ties were introduced to connect the walls to the floor.

Vertical ties were used to make structural connections between walls. Each precast concrete facade element had two horizontal tie-connections with the floor, as well as two vertical tie-connections with the facade elements above and below. The core walls had two or more tie-connections between walls and two or more tie-connections with the floor. The tie-connections are also visible in the shop drawings of the facade elements (Figure 72). The purple in the drawing indicates the inner load-bearing panel and the green parts represents the outer panel of the sandwich element. A sheet of insulation is positioned between the two concrete layers.

Figure 72. Precast concrete facade element (source: Province of Gelderland, amended).

The dimensions of the building are shown in (Figure 73 and Figure 74). Some details of the in-situ foundation beams are included in the drawing of the floor plan.

Figure 73. Floor plan of level 1 (source: Province of Gelderland, amended).

Figure 74. Cross section of the building (source: Province of Gelderland, amended).

The stability of the building was guaranteed by the concrete core in the centre of the building (part C) and two facade walls at the end of the wings of the building (facade at grid 1 in part A, and the facade at grid R in part B – Figure 75).

Figure 75. Floor plan of the building with all stability components (source: Province of Gelderland, amended).

4. 4. Deconstruction

The deconstruction was performed in three stages. The first stage was the deconstruction of the five-storey wing B of the building. The elements harvested from this wing are load-bearing facade elements and hollow core floor slabs. The second stage was the deconstruction of the top storey core elements and some exterior elements. The third and last stage was the deconstruction of wing A of and the core of the building. This was done storey by storey.

The core was deconstructed as the last item in each floor to maintain sufficient stability of the structure, including the part of the structure which was deconstructed. The deconstruction of each floor started at the end of the wings and progressed towards the core.

The following photographs provide an impression of the deconstruction process of the structure of the building. The photographs are divided into three subsections, one for each stage.

4.4.1. Wing B

Figure 76. Start of the deconstruction of the top floor of wing B (photo: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e).

Figure 77. Deconstruction of the top floor slab elements (roof) (photo: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e).

Figure 78. Two holes were drilled in each hollow core slab for lifting (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO, amended).

In each hollow core slab, two holes were drilled on one longitudinal side of the slab (Figure 77). In Figure 78, the holes are located on the left side of the slab, this means the slab on the right was removed first. To lift the elements up, a chain was threaded from the top through the hole and brought back up along the right side of the slab. This formed a lifting point at one end of the slab. The same was also applied on the other side, creating two lifting points for each slab.

Figure 79. Deconstruction of facade element of wing B (photo: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e).

The original lifting points (two anchors at the top of each element) were used to lift the walls and facade elements. The anchors were also used to connect two facade elements.

Figure 80. Transport of the facade elements with special transportation trestle (photo: Thijs Lambrechts).

Figure 81. Transport of the facade elements with special transportation trestle (source: Thijs Lambrechts, TU/e).

The outer layer of the facade element is positioned lower than the inner layer. The uneven geometry called for a special structure during transport of the elements (Figure 81).

Figure 82. Overview wing B during deconstruction (photo: Thijs Lambrechts).

Figure 83. The deconstruction of wing B is finalised (photo: Thijs Lambrechts).

4.4.2. Core elements

Figure 84. Overview of the core of the building (source: Lagemaat).

Figure 85. Overview of the core of the building (source: Lagemaat).

Figure 86. The deconstruction of core facade elements at the top storey of the building (photo: Lagemaat).

Figure 87. The deconstruction of core facade elements (photo: Lagemaat).

Figure 88. The deconstruction of a core element (photo: Lagemaat).

Figure 89. The deconstruction of a core element (photo: Lagemaat).

The top core elements have a different height from the other core elements. The horizontal joint is not located near the floor, but halfway up the floor. In Figure 89 this halfway horizontal joint was cut with a saw on a rail. The rail was mounted on the element below and was anchored to the wall with retrofitted concrete fasteners (Figure 88 and Figure 89).

4.4.3. Wing A and the core

Figure 90. Overview of the deconstruction of wing A (photo: Google Street view).

Figure 91. Overview of the deconstruction of wing A (photo: Lagemaat).

Figure 92. Deconstruction of the facade elements of wing A (photo: Thijs Lambrechts).

Figure 93. Deconstruction of the floor slabs of wing A (photo: Marcel Vullings).

Figure 94. Temporary bracing of the structure during deconstruction (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

All hollow core slabs were sawn free because of the structural topping on each floor. Two cuts were made at the end of each slab to disconnect them from the facade. Two longitudinal cuts were made to disconnect them from one another. The longitudinal cut did not penetrate through the slabs, but the cut was left 2 cm short. After cutting, the remaining 2 cm were broken off by hydraulically pushing one end of the hollow core slab up. For this, a special rig was used (Figure 93 and Figure 94). The two reasons for this method were:

- By making the cut less deep the wear on the diamond saw blades was reduced.
- By breaking the last 2 cm the cut went automatically through the original joint between two hollow core slabs and left the bottom edges of the hollow core slabs in tact.

Figure 95. Lifting of a core facade element (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 96. Sawing of the joint of wall and floor slabs (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 96 shows how core walls and floor slabs were cut with a saw. For the floors, a sawing machine was used. For the walls, a saw was mounted on a rail, which was fastened to the concrete wall with retrofitted concrete fasteners.

Figure 97. The core walls connected to wing A (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 98 Horizontal sawing of a core walls in joint (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 99. Deconstructed staircases and stair landings (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 99 shows the deconstructed concrete stair landings and stairs, which will be reused or recycled into coarse aggregates for new concrete.

Figure 100. Overview of the building site. The building is completely deconstructed (source: Lagemaat).

Figure 100 is the last one in the deconstruction series, and it shows the deconstruction site at the end of the complete deconstruction process of the building. In the foreground, the office wing A was located and at the back, the wing B (on the left) and the core (C) in the middle of the photograph. Only the ground floor and foundation are still visible. The deconstruction was concluded in December 2022.

4. 5. Storage of the harvested elements

Figure 101 shows an aerial view of the complete storage area of Lagemaat at Heerde. The storage contains all harvested elements from the Prinsenhof building. The distance between the deconstruction site and the storage is 49,5 km.

Figure 102 and Figure 103 show the storage of the precast concrete elements in more detail. An inventory of the harvested elements is presented in Table 3.

Figure 101. Top view of the storage of the elements at the Heerde (photo: Lagemaat).

Figure 102. The harvested hollow core slabs (photo: Thijs Lambrechts).

Figure 103. The harvested facade elements (photo: Thijs Lambrechts).

Table 3. Inventory of the harvested precast concrete elements of the Prinsenhof project (thumbnails: Lagemaat, photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Code	Type	Description	Thumbnail	Number of elements
G	Facade element	Sandwich facade element with a load-bearing inner layer, an insulation layer and a concrete outer layer.		343
G	Facade core element	Sandwich core elements with a load-bearing inner layer, an insulation layer and a concrete outer layer.		66
K	Core element	Core elements, a load-bearing inner wall.		67
V	Floor	Hollow core slabs.		549
T	Staircase	Staircase in the core of the building		18
B	Staircase landing	Landing for the stairs in the core of the building		26

4. 6. Available project documents

During the preparation of the Dutch deconstruction pilot, the office building 'Prinsenhof' in Arnhem, the following data was collected:

- The building permit by the municipality of Arnhem.
- Floor plans (scale 1:100) by the owner of the building.
- Technical specifications of the project by the contractor.

- Calculations of the foundation and ground floor of the building by the main structural engineer.
- Calculations of the structure of the building, including the foundation by the main structural engineer.
- Additional calculations of floors, by the main structural engineer.
- Drawings of the foundation of the building (1:100) by the main structural engineer.

- Floor plans of the core (1:50) by the manufacturer of the precast elements.
- A few details of the precast concrete structure (1:5) by the manufacturer.
- Floor plan with the connections foundation and precast concrete elements (1:100) by the manufacturer.
- Elevations of the building with the precast facade elements (1:100) by the manufacturer.
- Interior elevations of the building and parking (connected to the office building, but not part of the deconstruction, 1:100) by the manufacturer.
- Shop drawings of the precast concrete facade elements (1:10) by the manufacturer.
- Calculations hollow core slabs of nine floors by the manufacturer.
- Floor plans with the hollow core slabs (1:50) by the manufacturer.
- Calculations of the concrete pile by the manufacturer of the piles.

5. Germany

5.1. Description of the projects

Hohenmölsen

The 1st German donor building (Figure 105) is located in the city of Hohenmölsen. By the end of 2021 the regional housing company WObAU GmbH tendered the deconstruction of the building's roof and the upper two floors, retrofitting of new roof, as well as a general refurbishment of the interior and exterior (new piping, electrics, insulation, etc.) of the building. In February 2022, the deconstruction company and ReCreate industry partner Ecosoil Ost GmbH was commissioned to execution the deconstruction. Preparation work (e.g. setting up construction site equipment, gutting and chiselling work, scaffolding) started beginning of April 2022. The actual deconstruction of the prefabricated concrete elements started in May and ended by the end of June 2022.

The donor building (Figure 105) was constructed in the early 1980s according to plans of the precast system P-Halle (see Schulze, 1996) as part of the industrialized mass housing projects in the former German Democratic Republic (GDR). The structure of the building consists of prefabricated concrete elements (Figure 104).

Figure 104. Deconstructed and partially tested elements Otto-Nuschke-Straße 9-14, 06679 Hohenmölsen: external walls (AW A – AW D), load-bearing interior walls (IW, IWT, IW2T) and floor slabs DE36 and DE24 (source: BTU).

Figure 105. Overview of the German pilot project (photo: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

Großräschen

In the 4th quarter of 2023, a second deconstruction project started in Großräschen. ReCreate project partner Ingenieurbüro Jähne was engaged to prepare the tendering and supervise works. Furthermore, the second project partner Ecosoil Ost GmbH won the tender for deconstruction and retrofitting the roof of this building. The building (Figure 106) and its deconstruction resemble in some aspects the deconstruction of the donor building in Hohenmölsen, However, some differences also exist, which will be discussed.

Figure 106. Second donor building in Großräschen (source: A. Mettke, BTU).

5. 2. Location of the donor building

Hohenmölsen

The city of Hohenmölsen is located in the state of Saxony-Anhalt (Figure 107). The closest larger city is Leipzig, which is located about 40 km north. Hohenmölsen has a population of 9.400. The area around the city is an important extraction site for brown coal. With the government's decision to end the use of coal for generating electric energy in Germany by the year 2038, the region will undergo substantial economic change in near future.

Figure 107. Location of Hohenmölsen in Germany (source: Apple Maps).

Figure 108. Location of the donor building in Hohenmölsen (source: OpenStreetMaps).

Precast concrete apartment buildings, which were built as part of the former GDR's large-scale housing construction program between the 1960s and 1980s, are usually located on the outskirts of a city, but close enough to connect the old city centre. They were planned with vast green spaces surrounding them, as can be seen in the vicinity of the donor building (Figure 108).

Großräschen

The building, built in 1988, is located in Karl-Marx-Str. 7 in 01983 Großräschen, approximately 35 km south west of Cottbus (where the university, BTU is located, Figure 109 and Figure 110).

Figure 109. Location of second donor building (red mark), potential reuse pilot (golden mark), BTU (black mark), source: google maps.

Figure 110. Location of the donor building (source: google maps).

5.3. Donor buildings

5.3.1. Building geometry

Hohenmölsen

The donor building is 101,2 m long, 10,2 m wide and 15,8 m high and has five storeys. It is divided into six sections that are each serviced by one stairwell. Every stairwell gives access to three apartments per floor, totalling in 90 apartments for the whole building. Two of the three apartments on every storey in each building section have balconies facing south-east. This building has an inward sloping roof. Between the top floor and the roofing is an open space for installations. Figure 113 shows a 3D BIM model of the donor building project. At the bottom of Figure 111 a typical floor plan is presented.

Figure 111. 3D overview of the building and a floor plan (source: Christoph Henschel, BTU, amended).

In Figure 112, the floor plan of one section with the three apartments (A, B and C) can be seen in detail. Apartments A and B with the balconies have an area of 48,8 m² each (excluding the balcony area), whereas the middle apartment C has an area of 41,8 m².

Figure 112. Section of the floor plan of building type IW64 P-Halle (source: Schulze, 1996, amended)

Großräschen

The building was a six-storey residential building with one main entrance and belongs to the type 'WBS70 C-Altenwohnungen Mittelganghaus' from the housing construction program of the former GDR. This type of building consists of precast concrete floor slabs and sandwich wall elements, which are connected by welded joints.

The floor slabs of the WBS70 are solid concrete slabs and are reinforced in accordance with a span of 3,60 meters. Elements with longer spans were manufactured as prestressed concrete slabs. The slab thickness is generally 14,0 cm. The aforementioned elements are predominantly supported on two sides (edge elements on three sides). The floors are covered with a cement screed (up to 8,0 cm).

Maximum element dimensions are:

- wall elements 6,30 x 2,80 m
- floor elements 6,00 x 1,80 m (prestressed concrete) and
- floor elements 3,60 x 1,80 m (reinforced concrete)

The standard storey height is 2,60 m.

5.3.2. Structure of the buildings

Hohenmölsen

The structure of the donor building (type 'P-Halle', see Schulze, 1996 and Figure 113) is typical of the GDR panel buildings in the 'P' series. The longitudinal and transversal internal walls are load-bearing. The facade elements perpendicular to the long outer facade, are non-load-bearing and only support only their own weight. Additionally to the wall elements and floor slabs, there are precast concrete elements for the foundation, basement, balcony structures and roof structure. These secondary elements were not considered for reuse either because of their high specificity (roof cassettes), because they were in a bad shape due to weather exposure (balcony elements) or for the reason that they weren't deconstructed at all (foundation). The stability of the building is ensured by the interaction between the load-bearing walls and the floor slabs. Furthermore, the welded rebar connectors between interior walls, exterior walls and floor slabs ensure a structural system taking up e.g. tension forces by wind. In summary, according to Schulze (1996):

- The maximum weight of the precast concrete elements is 5,0 tons (50 kN).
- The construction system is a cross-wall construction.
- The span of the floor slabs is 2,4 m and 3,6 m.
- Facade elements are made of lightweight concrete, single-layer, 29 cm thick and surface-ready.
- The internal walls are made of concrete, are 15 cm thick and surface-ready.
- The non-load-bearing partition walls are made of concrete, 4 cm and 7 cm thick.
- The floor slabs are reinforced concrete, 14 cm thick and surface-ready.

In general, the connections in the donor building were designed in such a way that the rebar protrudes from the concrete element at certain position so that it could then be welded to the protruding rebar of the adjacent element. The welded joint formed in this way was then filled with lightweight mortar to protect it from corrosion (Figure 114 and Figure 115).

The floor slabs and the external wall were connected by a rebar rod of 10 mm diameter and 270 mm length (Figure 116). The rebar was welded onto the protruding rebar from the floor slab and wall, respectively. The protruding rebar was located in a recess both in the external wall and the floor slab so that the connection was not obstructing any other building parts. Afterwards the recess was filled with lightweight mortar.

The connection of two or three internal walls was made with the same principle of welding a short rebar rod onto the protruding rebar in the concrete elements. For each of the longitudinal connection of internal walls, rebar rods of 165 mm length and 10 mm diameter was welded onto the rebar of the internal wall. In the case of the connection of two longitudinal and one cross wall a flat steel strip (40/6 mm and 145 mm length) was welded onto protruding rebar as well as two rebar rods of 200 and 230 mm length in the cross wall (Figure 117). As was the case in the connections of the exterior walls, the additional flat steel strip was not found in the actual connections of the donor building. The connection area was filled with lightweight mortar after the connections were welded together.

Figure 113. 3D BIM model of the layers of the building (source: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

Connection
Exterior Walls
to
Interior Wall

Figure 114. Drawing of the connection of two external walls with one internal wall (source: adapted from VEB, 1965).

Figure 115. Real-life connection of two outer walls with an internal wall (photos: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

Figure 116. Connection of an external wall to a floor slab (source: adapted from VEB, 1965).

Connection
Interior Walls
to
Interior Wall

Figure 117. Connection of the two or three internal walls (source: adapted from VEB, 1965).

5. 4. Deconstruction

Hohenmölsen

As the deconstruction is a part of the building’s remodelling, it is a so-called partial deconstruction: only the two upper storeys were deconstructed (Figure 118). This was done while the lower three storeys were occupied. However, the residents had to leave their apartments during the working hours of, which were usually office hours. At the end of the shift, the residents were allowed to return.

Figure 118. 3D BIM model of the building, only the top two storeys of the building are deconstructed (source: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

The principle of the deconstruction process was to follow a specific sequence to deconstruct the building in a logistically and efficient manner. This meant that a complete section (roof, walls, top floor and the fifth floor) had to be removed first, before starting with the deconstruction of the next section's roof. With this sequence, the existing roof areas were still protecting the majority of the building against the weather. In addition, the crane and other equipment did not need to be moved horizontally, but rather vertically and, most importantly, locally. Workers and their tools were concentrated in one area. Progress continued as a terraced like deconstruction (Figure 119 to Figure 121). As soon as the third section had been started, the workers were able to start constructing a new roof in section number one.

The next photos (Figure 119 to Figure 122) give a condensed overview of the documented deconstruction process from a distance. The deconstruction started on the east facade next to the access road to the (de-)construction site. Work gradually progressed to the west side of the building.

Figure 119. Photo of the building after the start of the deconstruction, beginning of May 2022 (photo: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

Figure 120. The deconstruction mid-May 2022 (photo: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

Figure 121. The deconstruction mid-June 15, 2022 (photo: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

Figure 122. Photo of the deconstruction at the end of June 2022 (photo: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

The following section takes a closer look at the deconstruction processes. Figure 123 shows the removal of the internal, non-load-bearing walls and the chiselling of the screed. The screed had a thickness up to 75 mm (Figure 124).

Figure 123. Chiseled screed inside the building (photo: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

Figure 124. Measuring the thickness of screed (photo: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

Figure 125. Lifting floor slabs of first section (photo: Pascal Herrmann, BTU).

Figure 126. Lifting the temporary roof cover (photo: Pascal Herrmann, BTU).

The construction site included a working area in front of the building. The elements were temporary stored there and those that had no further reuse purpose were crushed into football-sized pieces on site (Figure 125). After each working day, temporary roofs (Figure 126) were placed on the open deconstruction section of the building. As the original protective roofing had already been removed at this point and the first three floors were occupied, the use of such a protective system was essential.

The stair elements – as shown in Figure 127 and Figure 128 – were removed by drilling holes in the concrete and lifting them by crane with chain hangers.

Figure 127. Preparation of the deconstructing the concrete staircase (photo: Jakob Fischer).

Figure 128. Lifting of a staircase, view from below (photo: Jakob Fischer).

Figure 129. Cutting of the rebar connection (source: Pascal Herrmann, BTU).

The connections of the precast concrete elements in the donor building were all done with the previously described welded connection of protruding rebar that was then filled with lightweight mortar (Figure 129). For the deconstruction these assembly steps had to be reversed: first the lightweight mortar was removed with a pneumatic drill and then the welded steel connections were cut with a blow torch (Figure 129). To lift the elements from the building, the original lifting anchors were used.

Figure 130. Lifting of a harvested element (photo: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

Figure 131. Storing of concrete elements on site (photo: P. Herrmann, BTU).

The elements which were planned to be reused in the German pilot project were marked and carefully removed, lifted and stored in a temporary storage on site (Figure 130 and Figure 131).

If an element did not meet the basic requirements for reuse in terms of quality assurance, the Ecosoil staff decided not to store them. Reasons for discarding an element were many and varied, for example if the connectors and other anchor systems are damaged, if there are suspicious cracks in the concrete element, if major spalling was detected or if there were other major damages to the concrete.

Großräschen

The following chapter gives an overview of the documented deconstruction processes. First steps before deconstruction of the structure, was chiselling out the screed (Figure 132) to get to the concrete ceiling slabs and its connectors and to minimize the load when lifting the elements to a later stage. This screed waste was collected and recycled separately, since it contains a high amount of anhydrite.

Figure 132. Demolition work, the breaking of the screed (photo: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

Figure 133. Removing of the roofing and the concrete roof elements (above). The (re)construction of a new roof with directly reused elements (below) (photos: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

After the removal of roof felt and insulation, the roof elements themselves were gently deconstructed for later direct reuse on the same building as an 'old, yet new' roof (Figure 133). The temporary storage was in range of the crane directly on site, as shown in Figure 134 to Figure 136.

Figure 134. Stored roof and facade elements. Roof slope panels on the left and exterior facade elements on the right (photo: A. Mettke [left], Jakob Fischer [right], BTU).

Figure 135. Stored roof elements, above the interior central gutter elements (photo: J. Fischer, BTU)

Figure 136. the storage area with different types of elements (photo: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

Figure 137. Props supporting top working level (left) and mini excavator on top working level (right), photos: Jakob Fischer, BTU.

A mini-excavator was used instead of hand-held power chisels due to the strength of the joint material and to reduce the physical strain and increase the occupational safety of workers. It was used not only to open joints between the elements, but also to chisel holes through the elements so that the crane's chain sling for lifting could be inserted later.

To support the extra load generated by the mini-excavator, especially during the working process (dynamic and vibrating loads), props, as in Figure 137 needed to be installed on the levels below.

As there was not enough space to store all the elements (roof elements for direct reuse as well as elements for reuse elsewhere), the footpath and parking spaces in front of the building had to be used, as shown in Figure 138 (right).

Figure 138. Overview of the project sign and the lifting of one harvested element (left). The temporary storage at the construction site (right), source: Jakob Fischer, BTU.

The following figures show the new roof finish with reused elements from this building. Since Ecosoil marked, deconstructed and stored the elements with a special system, the roof could be reconstructed with no major logistical issues.

Figure 139. In the foreground of the photo, the reconstruction of the apartment floor into a new roof. In the background, the two storeys that were deconstructed (photos: Jakob Fischer, BTU)

Figure 140. An interior view of the stairwell underneath a reconstructed roof structure (above). An exterior view of the same stairwell with the nearly finished roof structure (below) (source: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

5. 5. Storage of the harvested elements

Hohenmölsen

After the deconstruction, the recovered elements that were determined for reuse (Table 4) were transported to the intermediate storage site on the Eastern edge of the city, about 2 km from the deconstruction site (Figure 141).

Figure 141. Location of the intermediate storage site in Hohenmölsen (source: Apple Maps).

The transport itself was carried out by a special truck with loader crane and an 'A-frame'. The A-frame was used to transport the wall elements, as it was not logistically and structurally possible to stack them like the floor slabs. The difference between the two different transport systems can be seen in Figure 142 to Figure 146.

Figure 142. Transportation of ceiling panels (Photo: S. Yanilmaz, BTU).

Figure 143. Transport of the wall elements (photo: S. Yanilmaz, BTU).

Figure 144. 'A-Frame' on a truck for transporting wall elements (photo: S. Yanilmaz, BTU).

Figure 145: The storage of the harvested elements (photo: S. Yanilmaz, BTU).

Figure 146. The storage of the harvested elements (photo: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

Table 4. Inventory of the precast concrete elements harvested from the German deconstruction donor building (source drawings: Christoph Henschel, BTU).

Code	Type	Description	Thumbnail	Number of elements
AWA	facade element	outer wall of apartment unit		72
AWB	facade element	outer wall of apartment unit with door access to balcony		24

AWC	facade element	outer wall of apartment unit		12
AWD	facade element	outer wall of staircase		12
IW	inner wall element	load-bearing internal wall		44
IWT	inner wall element	load-bearing inner wall with one door		60

IW2T	internal wall element	load-bearing internal wall with two doors		12
DE36	floor slab	floor slab for apartment area		192
DE24	floor slab	floor slab for staircase area (140x2380x2380 mm)		36

Großräschen

At the time of writing of this report, the transportation of the elements had not yet taken place but were planned for near future. In total 100 elements were deconstructed for reuse, of which 88 elements go to a storage in Kolkwitz (Figure 109, golden mark) and 12 elements to a storage in Cottbus (Figure 109, black mark).

Figure 147 and Figure 148 show the finished partially deconstructed building, the deconstruction site, and the storage of elements and in mid-March 2024.

Figure 147. Front view of the building halfway through during the deconstruction. Left side the deconstruction of the top two storeys is finished and the new roof is constructed (photos: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

Figure 148. View of all the harvested elements (photos: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

5. 6. Available project documents

Hohenmölsen

For the preparation of the deconstruction work, a local engineering office was commissioned by the building's owner (WOBAU GmbH) to create architectural drawings of the existing structure and the envisioned new roof construction that would be implemented after the partial deconstruction of the two upper floors. These drawings were hand drawn.

Also the research team at BTU Cottbus Senftenberg did archival research and found a lot of planning materials for the building type at hand (P-Halle) in the special online archive for buildings of the GDR-era ('Spezialarchiv Bauen in der DDR - Informationszentrum Plattenbau') initiated by the German federal institute for research on buildings, cities and spaces (BBSR). These documents consisted of both general planning brochures for the building type as well as catalogues of each different element type (facade element, internal wall, floor slab, etc.). During the research it became apparent that changes had been made

to the construction details. One example of the change is the different execution of the connection as described before.

Specific drawings and planning documents of the building that was constructed in Hohenmölsen could not be found. The list of gathered documents:

Drawings from local engineer:

- Facades, north and west (1:200)
- Floorplans, 5th floor and roof (1:200)
- Details of roof elements (1:50)
- Floorplan of one building section with three apartments (1:100)
- Section of deconstruction part (upper 2 floors) (1:100)

Archival documents from the archive of BBSR:

- 'Typenbauelementekatalog Außenwandplatte' (catalogue of element types, here: facade elements, 147 pages)
- 'Informationskatalog Außenwandplatten' (information catalogue for facade elements, 25 pages)
- 'Typenprojektierung Außenwandelemente' (type development: facade elements, 66 pages)
- 'Typenprojektierung Geschossdeckenplatten' (type development: floor slabs, 44 pages)
- 'Typenprojektierung Innenwandelemente' (type development: internal wall elements, 74 pages)

6. Other deconstruction projects

During ReCreate, some ReCreate partners were also involved in other deconstruction projects, not part of the ReCreate project. The information and experiences of the other deconstruction projects is incorporated in the ReCreate research, because this provides valuable additional insight and data. In order to provide a complete overview of all the deconstruction projects used in the ReCreate research two additional projects are described in this chapter. The first additional project is a Dutch office building Ter Haak in Amsterdam, and the second additional project is a German block of flats in Grimma.

The information on the additional project presented in this chapter is not as extensive as for the proper ReCreate deconstruction pilots.

6.1. Office building Ter Haak

In ReCreate's Dutch reuse pilot, the elements of the 'Prinsenhof' donor building will be reused in a configuration very different from the original configuration. For the office building 'Ter Haak' in Amsterdam, the ReCreate partner Lagemaat opted for a different concept: reusing the building frame in its entirety in another location². This approach affects the deconstruction process, as it eliminates a big part the design process of a new building (Figure 149).

The building in the harbour of Amsterdam is the head office Ter Haak and was built in 2007. The office building is no longer in use and it was decided to deconstruct the building and reuse it.

Figure 149. Overview of the office building Ter Haak in Amsterdam (photos: Ter Haak Group).

² Note: No ReCreate project funding was used by Lagemaat for any work related to this deconstruction project.

6.1.1. Location of the donor building

The building was located at Ruijgoordweg 80, Amsterdam (Figure 150 and Figure 151). The storage facility of the harvested elements is at the moment at the same address.

Figure 150. Location of the office building 'Ter Haak' (source: Google maps).

Figure 151. Location of the office building 'Ter Haak' (source: Google maps).

6.1.2. Donor building

Building geometry

The building consists of a precast concrete structure and a steel structure on the top floor. The roof structure of the building is also a steel structure (Figure 152 and Figure 153). At the west side of the building, there is a steel lift structure, next to the building's main entrance. The building footprint is 36,8 m x 15,8 m and the total height is 17,5 m. The basement under the building is used for parking cars.

Structure of the building

The facade elements are precast concrete sandwich panels with a load-bearing inner layer. The outer layer consists of polished, coloured concrete. Between the two concrete layers is an insulation layer. Two different types of hollow core slabs were used in the building. The slabs with a long span are 260 mm thick, and the ones with a shorter span are 200 mm thick. A screed layer was applied on top of the slabs. The lift was a steel structure with concrete walls, the number of which varied per storey. Offset from the centre of the building was a row of round concrete columns with inversed T-beams made of concrete sitting on top (Figure 152, blue). One was a steel beam (Figure 152, green line) to provide extra space underneath the concrete floor for different types of installations, such as ducts and piping (Figure 153).

Figure 152. First floor plan of the 'Ter Haak' office building (source: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

The stability of the building was ensured by a concrete core on the south side of the building and facade elements acting as bracing walls on the north side. The steel and concrete structure of the lift did not participate in bracing the building.

Figure 153. Row of columns and beams, cf. Figure 152, photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO, amended).

6.1.3. Deconstruction

The deconstruction was performed in four stages. The first stage encompassed the stripping of non-structural components, such as suspended ceiling tiles, doors and doorframes, etc. The second stage was the deconstruction of the steel structure of the top floor and the lift structure. The third stage consisted of the deconstruction of precast concrete elements, such as facade elements, floor slabs, beams, columns, stairs, etc. The final stage was the demolition of the in-situ cast concrete basement (carpark). The concrete in the basement was crushed and recycled as a coarse aggregate in manufacturing new concrete. All the harvested concrete and steel components were placed in stock, awaiting reassembly in a new location.

The next photographs (Figure 154 to Figure 164) provide an overview of the deconstruction process of the precast concrete structure. In the photos the top two floors are already deconstructed and the next step is to deconstruct the precast concrete elements of the first floor. It should be noted that all the connections are cut in order to deconstruct the building. The connections are not demountable and cannot be reused, so the elements need to be reconnected in different way. The new connections and the foundation will be part of the (structural) design of the new building.

Figure 154. Overview of the donor building during deconstruction (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 155. Overview of the east-north side of the donor building (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 156. The deconstruction of a concrete beam sitting on a column and wall (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Before the beams were lifted, the connections were drilled out. This means that at the location of the beams' supports, the starter bars in grout tubes were drilled out by drilling a cylinder from the top of the beam to the bottom of the beam (Figure 157). In some cases, additional jackhammering was needed in order to get the beam loose.

Figure 157. The first beam is salvaged from the building. The starter bars in the columns are visible (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Like in the Prinsenhof project, all elements were labelled with a plastic label. The label provides project information and a unique code for each element. A QR-code is added to make the process of reading the labels simpler. The QR-code is linked to a database with additional information on the elements.

Figure 158. Labelling the harvested elements (a beam) (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 159. Labelling of concrete stairs with a steel railing (right). Left photo shows the original labelling of a precast concrete element done by the manufacturer. (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

After the deconstruction, several original labels were discovered (Figure 159, right). The original labels were applied by the manufacturer of the precast elements during the production process. They are paper labels that have been placed in wet concrete during the production but have survived to this day in a readable condition. The original labels also include some basic information of the element, like a unique element code and a barcode. The barcode also refers to a database with information. The manufacturer may be able to provide the element information.

Some of the elements, such as the hollow core slabs, were cleaned on-site by removing excess concrete or mortar. All the simple cleaning operations were performed on-site.

Figure 160. When cleaning is simple, some of the elements are cleaned on-site (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 161. Sawing of the longitudinal joint between hollow core slabs. In each slab, two holes have been drilled for the lifting chains (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 162. The sawing of the hollow core slabs results in a slurry of water and saw cutting. The slurry seeps down onto the floors below and on facade elements (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 163. Before deconstructing elements, other remaining elements are temporarily braced. Ladders and a mobile platform are used to reach all the elements (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 164. Equipment used in the deconstruction. On the right, a milling tool to remove the screed from the hollow core slabs. On the left, a jack hammer for removing pieces of concrete (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

6.1.4. Storage of the harvested elements

At the time of writing this report, the new location of the building was not known. Depending on the time necessary to determine the new location of the building, the elements may eventually be moved from the current location to a temporary storage facility. In this situation a temporary storage facility can be very simple, because the elements don't need to be refurbished. They only need to be cleaned and this can be done at the current location in Amsterdam.

Because the building as a whole will be rebuilt at another location, not only the concrete structure was harvested, but also all other structural and non-structural elements, such as the steel structure at the lift and the structure of the top floor.

Figure 165 to Figure 169 show the storage of different types of harvested elements on the site, and Table 5 gives their inventory.

Figure 165. Lifting of a harvested beam, moving it to the temporary storage of the elements on site (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 166. Overall view of the storage of harvested elements on the west side of the building (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 167. Storage of the hollow core slabs (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 168. Storage of all the other (structural) elements of the building (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Figure 169. Storage of facade elements (photo: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Table 5. An inventory of the harvested precast concrete elements of the office building 'Ter Haak. (photos: Marcel Vullings, TNO).

Code	Type	Description	Thumbnail	Number of elements
HCS	floor slabs	hollow core slabs with two different thicknesses		120
B	beams	precast concrete beams		16
BW	internal walls	precast concrete internal walls (stairwell and lift shaft)		24
G	facade elements	sandwich elements		68

K	columns	round precast concrete columns		16
T	stairs	precast concrete stairs		16
BD	landings	precast concrete stair landings		8
BW	parapet elements	parapet elements on the top floor		17

6.2. Block of flats in Grimma

6.2.1. Donor building

The ReCreate partner Ecosoil Ost GmbH engaged in another partial deconstruction project between April and July 2023³. The five-storey building, type WBS 70, was built in 1981, had 4 entrances and was fully vacant at the time of deconstruction (Figure 170). The building was renovated for the first time in 1990 and was provided with expanded polystyrene (EPS) thermal insulation (thickness 100 mm) ten years later. In this project, the upper two storeys and the roof elements were deconstructed and harvested, whereas the special roof elements were not reused again for the new roof structure, but were recycled. Furthermore, the complete balcony system was deconstructed.

Figure 170. Building before the deconstruction (photos: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

³ Note: No ReCreate project funding was used by Ecosoil Ost GmbH for any work related to this deconstruction project.

Figure 171. Building after the deconstruction (photo: Pascal Herrmann, BTU).

6.2.2. Deconstruction

In comparison to other deconstruction projects of precast concrete buildings from the former GDR era (such as the two pilots described in Chapter 5), this project was quite time-consuming and labour-intensive due to the preparatory work on removing the insulation that had to be carried out prior to the deconstruction of the precast concrete structure of the building. Especially for the deconstruction of the balconies, as shown in Figure 172, this insulation had to be stripped to reveal joints and connection points. During the deconstruction, all of the additional facade insulation was eventually stripped.

Figure 172. Removing insulation of facade elements (photos: Jakob Fischer, BTU).

All the usual deconstruction processes described in Chapter 5 apply one-to-one to this project in Grimma. These included:

- chiselling work to remove screed layer on each floor level
- cleaning and removing roof elements
- installing props to support the structure
- opening up joints and mortar locks to reach and disconnect connectors
- deconstructing sequencing
- etc.

The crushing of all concrete elements was taken place directly in front of the building in an enclosed area (Figure 173).

Figure 173: Crushing of concrete elements (left) and loading crushed material (right), photos: P. Herrmann, BTU.

7. Conclusion

The purpose of this report has been to describe the donor buildings and real-life deconstruction pilots of the ReCreate project: in Finland and the Netherlands, one each, and in Sweden and Germany, two in each. Two additional deconstructions, one in the Netherlands and one in Germany, were followed, observed, and described in the report to gain insights, even though they were not ReCreate's proper pilots. All the learnings acquired are reported in a centralised manner in another deliverable of the ReCreate project (see Vullings et al. 2024).

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